

BILINGUALISM AS A COMPLEX SCIENTIFIC PROBLEM

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Abstract. *The relevance of the study is confirmed by the high level of population migration and the development of two languages, which leaves an imprint on the psychological and linguistic component. Goal: to study bilingualism as a complex scientific problem. Methodology: a sample of 200 respondents, bilinguals who speak Russian and Uzbek languages and monolinguals, through questionnaires, cognitive tests and interviews. The analysis showed the positive impact of bilingualism on cognitive functions; knowledge of two languages develops intellectual and communication abilities.*

Keywords: *bilingualism, cognitive processes, psycholinguistics, cultural identity, multilingualism.*

Introduction

Bilingualism is a complex problem that covers both social, cultural and linguistic components. Domestic Russian bilingualism is acquired through training and communication with the population.

The relevance of the study is confirmed by the high level of population migration and the development of two languages in connection with these circumstances, which leaves an imprint on the psychological and linguistic component.

The object of the study is the personality of a bilingual, and the subject is the social, cultural and other aspects of studying the phenomenon of bilingualism.

The study covers the problem of insufficient knowledge of the impact of bilingualism on individuals and society.

The purpose of the study is to study bilingualism as a complex scientific problem.

The objectives of the study include:

1. Analysis of literary works on the topic;
2. Conducting empirical research;
3. Analysis of the results, taking into account the interdisciplinary aspect.

The research hypothesis consists of the statement that bilingualism contributes to the development of cognitive functions in an individual and an increase in the level of social communication and cultural identity.

Literature review

In the social aspect, the problem of bilingualism began to be studied since the late 20s of the last century, for example L.S. Vygotsky argued about the difficulties of multilingualism in childhood from a psychological, as well as a practical point of view [2]. Particular attention to this problem has begun to be paid in the last few years with the increase in the number of bilingual citizens due to migration due to political or social conditions.

Disputes on the issue of bilingualism are reflected between scientists from different fields of knowledge, for example speech therapists, linguists, sociologists and others, which has led to the absence of a single characteristic of this phenomenon. A. A. Leontyev spoke about the

cognitive side of language learning, since there is an indirect borrowing of national culture on the part of the student [4].

Cognitive functions in conditions of bilingualism were studied by R.K. Shakirov, D.M. Romanova in the context of native speakers of French and English. The authors note insufficient disclosure of this process and the many advantages of bilingualism [6].

The same problem is touched upon by Emirova M., noting the positive effect of bilingualism on the brain and its functions, such as attention control and task switching [7].

The main problems of the phenomenon of bilingualism were considered in the study of M. G. Danielyan, who studied the difference between bilingualism and multilingualism, where the first author refers more to the predominance of one of the languages in the process of communication, and to the second phenomenon the equal use of language systems without highlighting any one [3].

The problem of methodology for teaching Russian to bilingual children was reflected in the work of A.G. Maltseva, who highlights the key difficulties in learning a second language in children, the difficulties that parents face in such a situation [5].

This problem has not been ignored by foreign scientists either, so Chen S. [8] together with colleagues conducted a study to examine the capabilities of bilingual elderly people regarding their cognitive advantage over their monolingual peers, as well as the influence of factors associated with cognitive abilities (cognitive state of participants, assessed cognitive area) and factors associated with bilingualism (proficiency in a second language, frequency of use, acquisition time and immigration status of participants) on the cognitive advantage of bilingualism. The overall results of the meta-analysis showed that bilingualism had a slight cognitive advantage over monolingualism in elderly people.

Furthermore, subgroup analyses showed that factors such as participants' cognitive state, assessed cognitive domain, second language proficiency, acquisition time, and participants' immigration status influenced the cognitive advantage of bilingualism in older adults.

Leikin M., Tovli E., Woldo A. conducted a study on the interaction between bilingualism, executive functions and creativity in problem solving among adult male students [9]. The relationships between factors, namely the type of bilingualism (balanced and unbalanced bilingualism) and the type of creative thinking (convergent and divergent thinking) were studied. The results showed that Russian-speaking participants showed better results in the Torrance tests of creative thinking, especially in terms of flexibility and fluency.

In the Remote Association Test, balanced bilinguals outperformed unbalanced bilinguals in the English version and showed the same results in the Hebrew version of the test. In this case, significant correlations were found between the Remote Association Test results in all three languages in the Russian group. Thus, balanced bilingualism also seems to be characterized by a well-organized language system in which all of an individual's languages are interconnected. In addition, the results support the hypothesis that balanced bilingualism has a positive effect on divergent thinking.

They conclude that although the diversity of linguistic assumptions and approaches to defining bilingualism presents significant challenges, a concerted effort to systematize and synthesize research in this area may enable the creation of a valid and generalizable index of multilingual experience.

A number of authors classify bilingualism as a process, for example, bilingualism is considered as a mental phenomenon by E. M. Vereshchagin [1], where bilingualism is defined as the ability to express oneself in two languages of different systems, as well as to switch from one language to another in the process of communication.

This concept has different classification criteria (Fig. 1):

1. Age at which second language acquisition occurs: early and late (in adulthood) bilingualism
2. The number of actions performed on the basis of this skill: receptive bilingualism (when a bilingual person is limited only to understanding speech works belonging to the secondary language system); reproductive bilingualism (when a bilingual is able to reproduce what he read and heard); productive (producing) bilingualism (when a bilingual understands, reproduces and generates speech works belonging to the secondary language system).
3. The correlation of two speech mechanisms with each other: pure bilingualism (communication in the family is carried out in the native language, and in society - in another); mixed bilingualism, in which languages freely replace each other; natural bilingualism (from birth the child hears speech in two languages in the family); artificial bilingualism (learning of another language specially organized by the family).
4. From the point of view of the communicative sources of the formation of bilingualism, there are two models: contact bilingualism (occurs in the process of communication); non-contact bilingualism (formed in the absence of the possibility of contact in another language, under the influence of the media (for example, television)).
5. Communicative activity: active and passive bilingual. People who engage in active communication while learning a language that has become dominant can be considered active.
6. The method of connecting speech in each language with thinking: direct bilingualism; mediated bilingualism

Fig. 1. Criteria for the classification of bilingualism

Taking into account the given examples from the studies, it is worth mentioning the need to study this problem in a comprehensive manner from a theoretical and practical point of view. Most researchers talk about bilingualism as a level of proficiency in two languages to varying degrees of perfection, as well as a problem of conflict between languages in cultural and linguistic matters.

However, from a scientific point of view, researchers tend to have a positive assessment of bilingualism, which covers various fields of science and provides the opportunity for its interdisciplinary study, expanding knowledge about bilingualism at the intersection of sciences. At the same time, researchers are studying problems related to the relationship between the systems of two languages, the transition from one language to another, the differences and similarities of language systems.

Materials and methods.

To conduct an empirical study, a sample of 200 respondents was taken, of which one half are bilinguals who speak Russian and Uzbek, and the other half are monolinguals. Age of both groups: from 18 to 40 years. The study was conducted on the basis of a higher education institution.

Questionnaires, cognitive tests and interviews were used to collect data.

The questionnaire consists of the following questions:

1. Demographic information: age, gender, education level, place of work or study
2. Questions about language:
 - 1) What languages do you speak?
 - 2) What language do you use at home/work/study?
 - 3) How many years have you been using multiple languages in communication?

The following cognitive tests were used for the study (Fig. 2):

Fig. 2. Cognitive tests

During the interview, participants were asked the following questions:

1. How well do you think your communication skills are with people of another culture?
2. Do you often have to interact with representatives of other cultures?
3. Can you give an example of your intercultural communication?

Results

The following data were obtained from the survey:

The average age of the participants was 29 years, of which the average age of bilinguals was 28 years old, and monolinguals - 30 years old.

The proportion of men is 45%, women - 55%.

Bilinguals: men - 40%, women - 60%; monolinguals: men - 50%, women - 50%.

In terms of education, almost 65% of respondents have a bachelor's degree, 30% have a master's degree, and 5% of the sample are doctors of science.

About 60% are studying, 40% are working.

Regarding language use, 55% of bilinguals speak Uzbek at home, 30% at work and school.

The average time period for using two languages among bilinguals was 15 years.

During the first test, the first group showed 15% better results compared to monolinguals.

In the second test, bilinguals made fewer mistakes (by 20%).

In the last test, the working memory capacity also showed better results for the first group (by 10%).

According to the interview results, bilinguals communicate with representatives of other cultures 80% more often, which has a positive effect on their social and psychological function.

In addition, more than 70% of bilinguals note visible results of a high level of intercultural skills due to the mastery of two languages.

The analysis showed a positive impact of bilingualism on cognitive functions and communication skills between cultures, as well as in terms of human interaction.

Discussion

The influence of bilingualism on the processes under consideration is explained by the constant switching of a person between language systems, which develops cognitive functions and memory, as well as intercultural skills.

In the future, the study may touch upon such aspects as studying the influence of bilingualism on different age groups, on other cognitive functions of a person, as well as conducting an impact assessment in the long term.

Conclusion

Thus, it can be said that bilinguals note the positive impact of their skills on the flexibility of thinking and communication capabilities, while monolinguals may experience difficulties when interacting with representatives of other cultures.

Knowledge of two languages not only develops intellectual abilities, but also helps in the professional field and opens up great opportunities for career growth. Knowledge of Russian language helped bilinguals in their educational and professional activities. These results confirm the importance of bilingualism when studying it at the intersection of different sciences and its influence on many branches of scientific knowledge.

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